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RELATIONSHIP OF POSTOPERATIVE SCAR ON THE UTERUS AND TYPE II COLLAGEN.....9
2. **Khudoyarova R. Dildora, Shavkatova Z. Aziza**
OZONE THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PREGNANT WOMEN WITH FETOPLACENTAL INSUFFICIENCY.....17
3. **Todjjeva I. Nigina**
HYPERPLASTIC PROCESSES IN PREMENOPAUSAL AGE WOMEN.....28

ANESTHESIOLOGY AND REANIMATION

4. **Matlubov M. Mansur, Nematulloev K. Tukhtasin**
EVALUATION OF THE EXTERNAL RESPIRATORY FUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH VARIOUS DEGREES OF OBESITY IN THE PRE-OPERATIVE PERIOD.....35
5. **Pardaev K. Shukur, Sharipov L. Isroil, Kasparova A. Gayana**
USE OF COMBINED SPINAL-EPIDURAL ANESTHESIA IN SIMULTANEOUS GYNECOLOGICAL OPERATIONS.....44
6. **Sharipov L. Isroil, Pardaev K. Shukur**
ALTERNATIVE OPTION OF PREMEDICATION IN GYNECOLOGICAL PATIENTS DURING PERIMENOPAUSE (LITERATURE REVIEW).....52

SURGERY

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TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF STRUMECTOMY IN TOXIC GOITER.....61
8. **Sherbekov A. Ulugbek, Khadarova O. Laylo, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor**
INTEGRATED SURGICAL APPROACH TO PATIENTS WITH VENTAL HERNIATION AND OBESITY.....70
9. **Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Nazarov N. Zokir, Sulaymonov U. Salim**
OPTIMIZATION OF TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ELDERLY AND SENIOR PATIENTS WITH COMPLICATED FORMS OF CHOLELITHIASIS.....81
10. **Gulamov M. Olimjon, Mukhamedov Z. Batir, Tashkenbayev R. Firdavs, Dusiyarov M. Muhammad, Makhmudov B. Saydinjon**
STUDYING THE REASONS FOR THE FORMATION OF SKIN-PROSTHETIC FISTULAS AFTER HERNIOPLASTY OF THE ABDOMINAL WALL.....92
11. **Ahmedov K. Gayrat, Gulamov M. Olimjon, Makhsudov T. Maksud, Saydullaev Ya. Zayniddin, Khudaynazarov R. Utkir**
THE ROLE OF ENDOSCOPIC METHODS IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF GERD COMPLICATIONS.....99
12. **Babajanov S. Akhmadjon, Makhmudov B. Saidinzhon, Safarova B. Khafiza**
CRITERIA FOR CHOOSING A PLASTY METHOD IN PATIENTS WITH POSTOPERATIVE VENTAL HERNIAS.....105
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RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF BURN DISEASE IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS.....113

14. **Khayitov M. Laziz, Khakimov A. Erkin, Karabaev K. Khudoiberdi, Abrorov N. Shahbozjon**
THE RESULT OF INTENSIVE THERAPY OF MULTIPLE ORGAN FAILURE IN BURNED.....121
15. **Karaboev Sh. Dzhamshidkhon, Shakirov M. Bobir, Mizavov O. Furkat**
FEATURES OF THE TREATMENT SANDAL BURNS OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES.....129
16. **Elmuradov K. Golibjon**
MODERN VIEWS ON THE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CLOSED ABDOMINAL TRAUMA.....133
17. **Yuldashev Sh. Farrukh, Abdullaev A. Saifulla, Rakhimov M. Nodir, Shakhanova Sh. Shakhnoza**
FEATURES OF THE WOUND PROCESS IN DIABETES MELLITUS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....140

PEDIATRICS

18. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Ergasheva Y. Munisa**
MEDICO-SOCIAL ASPECTS OF CHILDHOOD DISABILITY.....148
19. **Rasulova A. Nodira, Rasulov S. Alisher**
MODIFIED APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF RICKETS IN THE CONDITIONS OF UZBEKISTAN.....156
20. **Mirrakhimova Kh. Maktuba, Saidkhonova M. Adibakhon**
CHANGES IN THE QUALITY OF LIFE INDICATORS OF PATIENTS WHEN ALLERGIC RHINITIS IS COMORBID WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN.....162
21. **Ulugbekova J. Gulrukh, Adkhamov A. Shokhjakhon**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GROWTH INDICATORS OF DACRYAL PARAMETERS IN SUBJECTS AGED 7-12 YEARS LIVING IN ANDIJAN CITY AND IZBOSKAN DISTRICT.....169

MORPHOLOGY

22. **Niyazov K. Norbek, Usmanov Dj. Ravshanbek, Akhmedova M. Sayyora, Nisanbayeva U. Aziza**
MORPHOLOGY OF THE PANCREAS GLAND ON THE BACKGROUND OF EXPERIMENTAL HYPOTHYROIDISM.....175
23. **Egamov J. Bunyodbek, Salaeva Sh. Zulfiya**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEY IN INFANTS WHO DIED FROM ASPIRATION SYNDROME.....181
24. **Boykuziev Kh. Hayitboy, Asadova Dj. Feruzakhon**
MORPHOFUNCTIONAL INTEGRATION OF NEUROIMMUNOENDOCRINE SYSTEMS.....185
25. **Oripov S. Firdavs, Dekhkanova T. Nilufar**
FEATURES OF A CREDIT-MODULAR SYSTEM IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES.....191
26. **Boboev I. Askar, Oripov S. Firdavs**
MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC CHANGES IN THE GALLBLADDER WALL IN DOGS WITH EXPERIMENTAL CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS.....195
27. **Usanov S. Sanjar, Korjavov O. Sherali, Kurbonova M. Latofat**
MORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LIVER TISSUE OF GROUP FOUR WHITE RATS.....201

NEUROLOGY

28. **Usmanova T. Parviza**
PECULIARITIES OF THE CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL COURSE OF CEREBRAL CIRCULATORY DISORDERS IN CHILDREN.....207
29. **Khakimova Z. Sahiba, Khamdamova K. Bakhora, Kodirov U. Arzikulovich**
MODERN CONCEPTS OF DEGENERATIVE DISEASES OF THE SPINE AND THEIR DIAGNOSIS.....214
30. **Khakimova Z. Sahiba, Kodirov U. Arzikulovich, Khamdamova K. Bakhora**
APPLICATION OF COMPLEX PHYSIOTHERAPY METHODS TO THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM DORSOPATHY.....222
31. **Rozzokov T. Dilmurod, Yugay A. Igor, Ibodullaev U. Saydullo, Matmurodov Zh. Rustambek**
TREATMENT BASED ON CLINICAL, NEUROLOGICAL AND INSTRUMENTAL DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA FOR PERIPHERAL NERVE DAMAGE(LITERATURE REVIEW).....229
32. **Xakimova Z. Sohiba, Akhmedova Z. Charos**
CHRONIC ISCHEMIA OF THE BRAIN - RELEVANCE OF MODERNITY.....234

THERAPY

33. **Agababyan R. Irina, Kobilova A. Nigina**
CHANGES IN THE LEVEL OF C-REACTIVE PROTEIN IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION WHILE TAKING COLCHICINE....240
34. **Agababyan R. Irina, Yusupova K. Zumrad**
POSSIBILITIES OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION CONTROL IN OVERWEIGHT PERSONS.....246
35. **Yarasheva Kh. Zarrina, Rustamova B. Sarvinoz**
OUTCOMES OF CORONARY ARTERY STENTING IN ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE.....252

STOMATOLOGY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

36. **Boymurodov A. Shukhrat, Rizaev A. Jasur, Abdurakhmonov R. Farkhod.**
PECULIARITIES OF THE COMBINED INJURIES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION.....260
37. **Nilufar B. Islamova, Nodira Sh. Nazarova**
RESEARCH CASES IN WOMEN AFTER MENOPAUSE CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN ORAL ORGANS AND THEIR ANALYSIS.....264
38. **Shaymatova R. Azizakhon, Gafforov A. Sunnatullo**
THE STATE OF THE MOUTH IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH DIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA.....270

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

39. **Nuraliev A. Nekkadam, Nazarov E. Jalolitdin Sulton, Sayfutdinov A. Zayniddin**
FEATURES OF THE STUDY OF GENETIC MUTATIONS IN M. TUBERCULOSIS FOR THE EMERGENCE OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE: A LITERATURE REVIEW.....280

FORENSIC-MEDICAL EXAMINATION

40. **Indiaminov I. Sayit, Zhumanov E. Ziyadulla**
POSSIBILITIES OF APPLICATION OF POST-MORTHER CHANGES IN THE LIVER
STRUCTURES TO ESTABLISH THE DATE OF DEATH.....289

ENDOCRINOLOGY

41. **Babadjanov D. Bakhtiyar, Matmurotov J. Kuvondik, Sattarov S. Inayat, Ruzmetov A. Bakhtiyar, ATAJONOV Sh. Tulkinbek**
COMBINED ENDOVASCULAR INTERVENTIONS FOR LESIONS OF THE
PERIPHERAL ARTERIES OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES ON THE BACKGROUND OF
DIABETES MELLITUS.....303
42. **Khalimov A M. Khanifa, Matmurodov J. Rustambek, Umirova M. Surayyo**
EVALUATION OF THE DYNAMICS OF DIABETIC POLYNEUROPATHY IN PATIENTS
AFTER COVID-19.....310

PEDIATRIC SURGERY

43. **Ulugmuratov A. Azim, Mavlyanov Sh. Farxod, Mavlyanov X. Shavkat, Ulugmuratov A. Firdavs**
STATUS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN CHILDREN WITH
INVAGINATION OF THE FINE INTESTINE (REVIEW OF LITERATURE).....315
44. **Khamraev J. Abdurashid, Eminov I. Ravshanjon**
FEATURES OF CLINICAL COURSE AND TACTICS OF TREATMENT OF
HEMORRHOIDS IN CHILDREN.....320
45. **Shamsiev A. Jamshid, Atakulov J. Ostonakulovich, Yusupov A. Shukhrat, BAyzhigitov I. Nusratilla**
HIRSCHSPRUNG'S DISEASE IN CHILDREN AND FEATURES REHABILITATION
AFTER SURGERY.....326

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

46. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Boymurodov A. Shukhrat, Abdurakhmonov R. Farkhod.**
REABILITATION OF THE COMPLICATIONS OF THE COMBINED SOFT TISSUE
INJURIES IN THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION.....332
47. **Ravshanova Z. Maftuna, Axmedov A. Ibrat**
REHABILITATION METHODS FOR TRAUMATIC INJURIES OF THE ANKLE JOINT IN
FOOTBALL PLAYERS.....336
48. **Egamova T. Malika, Rasulov Sh. Jamshedjon**
ORGANIZATIONAL MECHANISM FOR THE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH
CEREBRAL PALSY AT HOME.....341
49. **Egamova T. Malika, Rasulov Sh. Jamshedjon**
PHYSICAL REHABILITATION FOR CEREBRAL PALSY HOME.....345
50. **Xakimova Z. Sohiba, Gulyamova A. Gulshan**
USING FRACTIONAL LASER ABLATION TO IMPROVE THE CONDITION OF THE
SKIN AROUND THE EYES FOR THE PURPOSE OF REJUVENATION.....349

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FEATURES OF A CREDIT-MODULAR SYSTEM IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

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ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to the functioning of the credit-modular system in medical universities. The article gives a quick introduction of the fundamental ideas and describes the methods for teaching medical skills using a credit modular system as well as three divisions are given according teaching in modular system. In addition, several notions are provided regarding the assessment of student in teaching process and in an exam that based on the point-rating system.

Keywords: credit-modular system, credits, modules, academic discipline, introductory, basic, supplementary, modular learning.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ КРЕДИТНО-МОДУЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В МЕДИЦИНСКИХ ВУЗАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена функционированию кредитно-модульной системы в медицинских вузах. В статье дается краткое введение в фундаментальные идеи и описываются методы обучения медицинским навыкам с использованием кредитно-модульной системы, а также приводятся три раздела в соответствии с преподаванием по модульной системе. Кроме того, приводится несколько понятий, касающихся оценки студента в процессе обучения и на экзамене, основанных на балльно-рейтинговой системе.

Ключевые слова: кредитно-модульная система, кредиты, модули, учебная дисциплина, вводное, базовое, дополнительное, модульное обучение.

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Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

TIBBIYOT UNIVERSITETLARIDA KREDIT-MODULLI TIZIMNING XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqola tibbiyot oliy o'quv yurtlarida kredit-modul tizimining faoliyatiga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada asosiy fikrlarga qisqacha kirish berilgan va kredit-modul tizimidan foydalangan holda tibbiy ko'nikmalarni o'rgatish usullari tavsiflanadi, shuningdek modul tizimida o'qitish bo'yicha uchta bo'lim haqida fikrlar yuritilgan. Bundan tashqari, o'quv va imtihon jarayonida ball-reyting tizimidan talabani baholashga oid bir qancha tushunchalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kredit-modulli tizim, kreditlar, modullar, o'quv intizomi, kirish, asosiy, qo'shimcha, modulli o'qitish.

Introduction. In today's culture, integration processes are affecting more and more aspects of life. Higher education in Uzbekistan, in particular, cannot be separated from European integration.

Uzbekistan's educational strategy reflects national objectives in the sphere of education while also taking into consideration global trends that need considerable reforms in the education system.

The building of the educational process on the basis of a credit-modular system enables you to structure the educational process in line with Uzbekistan society's new expectations.

Based on a competence-based approach, the educational program assumes that medical graduates acquire theoretical knowledge of a specific academic field, practical and operational application of knowledge to specific situations, and values as an integral part of social interaction and life in society.

The credit-modular learning system is an educational process organization concept based on the integration of modular learning technology and credit educational units (credits). Training on the credit-modular system organizes students' assimilation of educational material in a discrete mode in accordance with a pre-developed modular program, which consists of logically completed parts of the educational material (modules) with the structural content of each module and the system of assessing students' knowledge [1].

The credit-modular system provides advantages and is seen to be a way to increase student mobility throughout the transition from one curriculum to another, including postgraduate education programs. The credit-modular system enables students to select the needed number of academic disciplines for study and assimilation, as well as to commit to assimilation within a specific time frame [2].

The credit-modular system provides for:

- modular structure of the educational program;
- use of credit units (credits) to assess labor intensity;
- the use of point-rating systems for assessing knowledge;
- participation of students in the formation of an individual curriculum;
- increasing the share of self-learning in the educational process;
- increasing the flexibility of educational programs.

The content of the discipline is split into substantive modules (2-4 modules per semester) with a credit-modular system of educational process organization, i.e. the academic discipline is established as a system of content modules. A module is a completed and recorded portion of an educational and professional program (academic discipline, practice, state certification) that is executed through proper forms of the educational process.

E.N. Solovova defines the notion of a module as follows – “this is a course or its autonomous part, having the necessary software and educational and methodological support sufficient to build various educational trajectories within its framework, easily connecting with other modular courses, if necessary, capable of changing in content / form / volume due to the initial flexibility of the internal structure” [3, p. 65].

Hence, the content module should contain time for lectures, seminars, practical and laboratory courses, independent and individual work (for example, coursework), consultations, practices and knowledge control on the module (current and final testing).

The fundamental differences between modular training and other types of training are in the following provisions:

- the content of the training is presented in complete, independent, complex modules, which are simultaneously a bank of information and a methodological guide for its assimilation;
- the interaction of the teacher and the student in the educational process is carried out on a fundamentally different basis – with the help of modules, students are provided with a conscious independent achievement of a certain level of preliminary preparedness for each pedagogical meeting;
- the very essence of modular training requires the inevitable observance of priority subject-subject relationships between the teacher and students in the educational process [4].

Credits are assigned based on the outcomes of training and the difficulty of the academic load throughout the academic year in full-time study. The academic burden is typically 1800-2000 hours per academic year, and one credit equates to 30 hours of total labor intensity.

Individual students (full-time or part-time study) are given credits after completing a formal training program (or a separate module) and getting a favorable assessment of the desired learning results.

While teaching a medical skill, the modules should be divided into introductory, basic, and supplementary. The initial lesson also includes required testing to establish the amount of “residual” knowledge. The fundamental module specifies the information, skills, and abilities that must be developed or reinforced. The learner obtains a set amount of points for each topic. When you finish your homework, you earn points.

The point-rating system of knowledge assessment provides for a 100-point scale, i.e. 100 points is the maximum number of points that students can receive for academic success in the process of studying a meaningful module. The assessment of knowledge for the content module takes into account the grades received for all types of classes conducted, for current and final testing (for example, for practical, laboratory classes, etc.), taking into account weight coefficients. The total assessment of the assimilation of the discipline's teaching material is determined without a semester exam as an integrated assessment of the assimilation of all content modules, taking into account weight coefficients [5].

The point-rating system is designed to increase the objectivity and reliability of the assessment of the level of training, is one of the elements of education quality management [6].

The point-rating assessment system enables students to: understand the system of forming assessments for disciplines and other types of employment in order to obtain final grades; recognize the need for systematic work on curriculum implementation based on knowledge of their current rating assessment for each discipline and its change due to untimely mastery of the material; and timely assess the state of their work on discipline study, implementation, and implementation; make changes to the structure of existing independent work during the training session.

In turn, a point rating system allows the teacher to: plan (in detail) the educational process for a specific discipline and stimulate student work for systematic work; make timely adjustments to the organization of the educational process based on the results of the current rating control to objectively determine the final assessment of the discipline, taking into account systematic work; and ensure the gradation of the assessment of the level of knowledge competency.

The following are the conditions for obtaining points: the minimum or maximum number of points is determined by the student's activity in the classroom, timely and high-quality completion of tasks; active academic work is encouraged by an additional point; additional types of educational activities are not mandatory and are performed at the student's request; for students absent from classes for good reason, an oral interview with the teacher on the topics is established.

Innovative methods of education, such as the ongoing use of computer technology, become especially significant when teaching medical skills on the basis of a credit-modular system. This is because multi-level workouts and activities with a credit-modular method of teaching medical skills are required. The use of computer technology simplifies the process of identifying the level of training and selecting the appropriate activities and exercises related to the degree of knowledge.

Conclusion. To summarize, the credit-modular system of education fully meets society's requirements for educational quality; the use of a credit-modular system can significantly increase

students' academic success; and the effective use of a credit-modular system in teaching a medical skills allows students to form medical experiences and decision-making capacity competency by organizing the transition from reproductive knowledge acquisition to self-expression.

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